

Strategic Thought of Liddell Hart and its Relevance in Contemporary Time

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Abstract: The research investigated the strategic thought of Liddell Hart and his strategy of the indirect approach. Each state has its different political objectives to achieve these objectives states may adopt Liddell Hart's thoughts according to its need. this study aims to determine how Sir Liddell Hart's thoughts influence the state's strategic community to shape their strategy in the light of Liddell Hart. This study examined why the limited war and the Strategy of Indirect approach are used to achieve political objectives. The study explores his strategic thoughts are changing contemporary warfare. US and Iran used their thought to achieve political objectives. Iran and US had a limited war. Azerbaijan won the war in a limited time with limited loss by applying his strategy of indirect approach in response Armine also used Liddell Hart's strategic thoughts to achieve its goals. The best application of his approach is Hybrid warfare; India is using hybrid warfare against Pakistan. Every state has different domestic and international political objectives they apply the strategic thought of Liddell Hart according to their available resources to achieve goals.

KEYWORDS; Liddell Hart, Strategic Thoughts, Strategy of Indirect approach, Political objectives, limited war

1. Introduction and Background of the study

Sir Basil Liddell Hart was born on October 31, 1895. He is known as Alchemist of War. He got his early education from St. Paul's School and Corpus Christi College, Cambridge and left it and left on the outbreak of the First World War to join the British Army During world war 1 and he developed his theory of war. He became an officer in the King's Own Yorkshire Light Infantry. In 1920 he wrote the Army's official Infantry Training manual. Which included his "battle drill" system and "expanding torrent" method of attack, which introduced infiltration tactics in 1917-18. With the use of gas warfare, millions of people faced health issues and he also got retirement from the military He always advocated Airpower and mechanized tank warfare. He emphasized the elements of mobility and

surprise. Liddell Hart retired as a captain in 1927. Liddell Hart was the author of several military biographies, several works on military strategy, and a history of World War II. In his articles and books, Liddell Hart became the world's leading exponent of using tanks as an independent striking force to make deep penetrations into enemy territory, cutting off enemy troops from their supplies and high command. His influential "indirect approach" was first announced in 1927 that indirect approach was much more an attitude of mind than an arrow on the map that the enemy had to be unhinged before he could be unmanned.

- 1-Adjust your end to your means
2. Keep your object always in mind -to achieve a goal by any means it
3. Choose the line (of course) of least expectation - Think of what course the enemy will consider the least probable.
4. Exploit the line of least resistance - "The longer the distance that has to be covered, the greater the ratio of natural obstacles, but the less the ration of opposition."
5. Take a line of operation which offers alternative objectives - This should not be confused with pursuing a single objective. - Refers to putting the enemy of the "horns of a dilemma."
6. Ensure that both the plan and dispositions are flexible – adaptable to circumstances - This refers to concentration and the ability to ensure elements/units can be mutually supportive. LH discusses the concept of concentration in greater detail and considers it a fundamental factor in success. For example, "True concentration is the fruit of calculated dispersion." Negative:
7. Do not throw your weight into a stroke whilst your opponent is on guard –waste of energy, manpower, and military hardware if you attack your opponent where he is prepared to defend with his full force, or it is an area where the opponent is confident to defeat you whenever you make the mistake of an attack. Maneuver your forces and surprise it where he is not sure an attack can happen.
8. Do not renew an attack along the same line (or in the same form) after it has once failed –do not attack an enemy again was it strong and defending itself it would be a waste of manpower, and military hardware and repeatedly will shelter the moral of the army the chance of more casualties because the same mistakes would be repeated enemy will take full advantage of it during the confrontation

He saw the failure of the German-French war as the protected, prolonged with endless confrontation. He studied and experienced both the world war and the cold war. Liddle Hart thinks that strategy is the practical adaptation of means placed at general disposal to attainment the object. Liddell hart defined strategy as the art of distributing and applying military means to fulfill the end policy. the strategy is not merely with the movement of forces, but also with the effect it creates. A British military historian and strategist known for his advocacy of mechanized warfare. According to Liddell Hart military is responsible to the government employing it and allows the government to intervene in strategy, amend it, and push it in a direction that may not simply be the overthrow of an enemy's military. The main purpose of war is subduing the enemy army on the Battlefield. Liddell Hart emphasized the importance of maneuver, technology in combat, and surprise. The aim of the nation in war is therefore to subdue the enemy's will to resist, with the least possible human and economic loss to oneself .he wrote a books some are as follows.

- Strategy
- Colonel Lawrence, the Man Behind the Legend

- The Science of War: Back to First Principles
- A History of Modern Wars of Attrition
- On Infantry
- Biographical Dictionary of World War 2

Theoretical Framework

Limited War Theory

The limited war was founded by Liddell Hart after world war I in which 60,000 people gave their lives and many others were physically disabled. The main purpose of war is subduing the enemy army on the Battlefield. Liddell Hart emphasized the importance of maneuver, technology in combat, and surprise. The aim of the nation in war is therefore to subdue the enemy's will to resist, with the least possible human and economic loss to oneself. The main pillar of limited war is as follows

(a)geographic scope: global or world war versus limited or local war; (b) ends or objectives: unconditional surrender or destruction of the opponent versus limited objectives, such as troop withdrawal or negotiated compromise; (c) means making restrained use of military capabilities or limiting attacks to specific targets, such as the distinction between counterforce and counter city attacks.

1.1 Significance of the Study

The significance of the current study is that the strategic thought of Sir BLiddell Hart is still relevant. His strategic thought influences the strategic community of every nation. the rival strategic move whether they are direct approach or indirect approach (Liddell hart) Liddel IHart strategic thought give various options to take counter options. In the age of missile, nuclear weapon, advanced military hardware, weaponization in space, climate change, globalization, international law, international organization (UN, EU), human rights activist, and nuclear umbrella nation cannot afford any direct hostility. So, Liddell hart's strategic thought guide today's strategist on how to behave in this complex world environment to attain maximum political objective thought minimum use of mean. This study will help the strategic community to understand the importance of limited war and the strategy of the indirect approach. This literature is useful for the students of defense and strategic studies to understand the Liddell hart strategic thoughts and its reverence in the contemporary world.

1.2 Hypothesis

Sir B.H Liddell's hart strategic thought changes the strategy of the nation to achieve the political objective through the indirect approach. In the age of missile, nuclear weapon, advanced military hardware, weaponization in space, climate change, globalization, international law, international organization (UN, EU), human right activist, and nuclear umbrella nation cannot afford any direct hostility so the study will investigate how Liddell hart strategic

thought are still relevant especially how limited war and the strategy of Indirect Approach will help nations to attain their political objective with the use of minimum use of resources and avoiding bloody war.

1.3 Research objectives

Sir Liddell Hart participated in world war 1 he saw a huge number of casualties. In world war 2 he criticizes Great Britain's strategy. he was an advocate of limited war; the purpose of limited war was to reduce the number of casualties. his theory of limited war, the strategy of indirect and approach moderate peace influence the contemporary strategies. Keeping in view his strategic thought following are the main objective of the study. Study will investigate the relevance of Liddell hart's strategic thought in the contemporary world. Study will examine the influence of Sir B.H Liddell Hart's strategic thought are changing contemporary warfare. Study will carry out the indirect approach is used to achieve a political objective.

1.4 Research Questions

Why Liddell Hart's strategic thoughts are still relevant?

Why the strategy of the indirect approach is often used to achieve a political objective?

How Liddell Hart strategic thoughts are changing contemporary warfare?

1.5 Core Question

How limited war help states to achieve their political objectives?

2. Literature review

A vast material was found to analyze the strategic thought of Sir B. H Liddell Hart and his thought relevance in current world politics. Data is collected by different articles, journal articles, and websites to understand his thought. Shekhar Duta Chief editor of "The Print" wrote in his article "How drones helped Azerbaijan defeat Armenia and the implications for future modern warfare". In his article, Sir Liddell Hart Strategic Thought of Indirect Approach applied Azerbaijan and Armenia fought a war for 44 days in which Azerbaijan use drones and AN2 against Armenia tanks and trenches. From this, we conclude that Azerbaijan took Liddell saying take the least resistance and airpower Azerbaijan took full advantage of Airpower against tanks and trenches. Azerbaijan lost 1/6 of Armenia lost because of the use of drones against the tanks. Colonel (Red) Phillip Mellinger's article Basil H. Liddell Hart: His Applicability to Modern War¹ in which he explains the relevance of Liddell Hart Strategic thought and also compares Clausewitz thought. He explains the thought of Liddell Hart on airpower the use of airpower is decisive in wartime. Air powers allow destroying of the enemy and it allows the strategist to avoid trench warfare. Liddell hart examines 280 campaigns which was carried out with a direct approach and they badly failed and huge human cost by adopting the

direct approach. At last, he argues Sun Tzu and Clausewitz had a different approach. BBC News gave the news on how Major General Soleimani was killed. Liddell Hart's indirect approach was used. The US attacked with a drone and killed Iran's leader of the Revolutionary Guard, Qasim Soleimani: the US kills a top Iranian general in a Baghdad airstrike² "Major General Soleimani" and nine in Iraq near Baghdad airport. In response Iran attacks US air bases in Iraq.

The US attacked Major General Soleimani because he was the mastermind in the proxy war in Syria and Iraq against them. The US took an indirect approach to kill Major General Soleimani because by drone it was difficult for Major General Soleimani's guard to retaliate with a drone. This gives us evidence that Sir B.H Liddell Hart's words for airpower are relevant. It was easy to target for the US to kill them in Iraq instead of killing him in Iran because the more likely Iran could see any drone breaching the sovereignty of Iran and might resist and shoot down the drone before attacking or after attacking Major General Soleimani. Dr. Can Kasapogal wrote the article "Analysis-Five key military takeaways from Azerbaijan-Armenia war³". He wrote Armenia adopted Sir Liddell Hart's strategy of indirect approach by choosing the line (of course) of least expectation and Exploiting the line of least resistance by attacking the population of Azerbaijan which creates intra-war deterrence.

3 Research methodology

Keeping in view the research problem in this study the qualitative research method will be used for collecting primary and secondary data. This study is primarily based on the concept of regional, defense, and strategic studies and international security. The data used in this study is from secondary sources in which journals, newspapers, books, and other articles are used to conduct the research. The qualitative method is used for the collection of data because this research is based on ideas, experience, analysis, assumptions, and critical thinking. No numerical data or experiments are not used to explain what is done in this research paper. The main argument of the study is the relevance of Liddell Hart strategic thought in the contemporary world. The hypothesis of this research is not testable because this is qualitative research. The hypothesis is leading to research.

4 Analyses

4.1 The limited war between Iran and the US

The US attacked with a drone and killed Iran's leader of the Revolutionary Guard "Major General Soleimani" and nine others in Iraq near Baghdad airport. In response, Iran attacks US air bases in Iraq. The US took an indirect approach to kill Major General Soleimani because by drone it was difficult for Major General Soleimani's guard to retaliate with a drone. This gives us evidence that Sir B.H Liddell Hart's words for airpower are relevant. It was an easy

target for the US to kill in Iraq instead of killing him in Iran because the more likely Iran detects any drone which is breaching the sovereignty of Iran and might resist and shoot down the drone before attacking or after attacking Major General Soleimani.

In response Iran also adopted the same indirect approach to take revenge on Major General Soleimani, Iran could not attack the mainland USA because they were if any kind of attack on the mainland of the USA, USA selected 52 sites including cultural site. Iran had five possible options to take revenge they might hurt the USA and UK economic interest by attacking a ship in the Persian Gulf or the straits of Hormuz second, they just kept silent and do not take any military action, third UN as they raised in UN, four they can attack Israel and they could attack US allies in the Middle East like Saudi Arabia, UAE, and others But Iran retaliatory attack in Iraq airbase on US troops. They also adopted an indirect approach and surprise the US and allies in the Middle East because attacking the USA mainland will be suicide for Iran, so they select an option that was the least resistant.

This case study shows the Sir B.Liddell Hart strategy of the indirect approach is relevant to achieve political objective.

4.2 The limited war between Azerbaijan and Armenia

Azerbaijan and Armenia fought a war for 44 days in which Azerbaijan use drones and AN2 against Armenia's tanks and trenches. From this, we conclude that Azerbaijan took Liddell saying take the least resistance and airpower Azerbaijan took full advantage of Airpower against tanks and trenches. Azerbaijan lost 1/6 of Armenia lost because of the use of drones against the tanks. Armenia attacked the population as the population cannot resist. They tried to create intra-war deterrence by adopting the indirect approach of Sir Liddle. The indirect approach fits in the case of Azerbaijan and Armenia. Azerbaijan kept its goal in mind they took the Nagorno Karabagh case to the UN and they also modernize their military which supported in war with Armenia in Nagorno Karabagh Azerbaijan sent AN2drones to Armenia and they thought big threat they activated their air defense which kept a busy air defense system during this Azerbaijan arm drone went and hit the target's tanks and trenches. Which completely shatter the morale of Armenian soldiers and they did not have any time to save their lives. This is also evidence that the Liddell approach is relevant and making the possible for nations to get their political objectives.

5 Conclusion

Liddell Hart saw both world wars in which millions of people lost their life. He gave the Grand strategy, the strategy of an indirect approach to achieve political objectives. The main purpose of war is subduing the enemy army on the Battlefield. Liddell Hart emphasized the importance of maneuver, technology in combat, and surprise. The aim of the nation in war is therefore to subdue the enemy's will to resist, with the least possible human and economic loss to oneself. Iran US and Azerbaijan Armenia war limited war fought to achieve a political objective. Azerbaijan Armenia and US Iran had limited war by using the strategy of the indirect approach.

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